

BETWEEN EARTH AND WATER

Clay as a symbolic operator
of cultural landscape

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ABSTRACT

The centrality of the visual dimension in understanding cultural landscape tends to obscure the symbolic and relational dimensions that also constitute it. This article proposes clay as a symbolic operator of cultural landscape, exploring its liminal condition between earth and water as a guiding thread for an analysis of forms of heritage that escape regimes of visibility, with the aim of rethinking landscape beyond its fixation on visible and durable forms. The article adopts a qualitative and essayistic approach, drawing on literary works, artistic practices, and theoretical frameworks as modes of access to the sensory and relational dimensions of landscape. Drawing on the thought of Ingold and Bispo dos Santos, it proposes that inhabiting the landscape means participating in its formation. In dialogue with Evaristo and Vieira Junior, the article examines how the materiality of territory can inscribe belonging, be denied as a right, or be experienced as a wound upon the body. Clay is then articulated with the symbolic through the figure of Nanã, an orisha in Yoruba cosmology, and through the work of Tostes. The conclusion argues that the concept of cultural landscape requires recognizing an interiority within things, capable of addressing and returning the gaze. Preserving a living landscape, in this sense, does not mean fixing it in durable forms, but sustaining the relational and experiential conditions through which it continues to emerge — a perspective that demands a reassessment of the criteria and instruments of cultural heritage protection beyond visible and stable forms of record.

Keywords: cultural landscape; materiality; embodiment; performance; anima mundi

INTRODUCTION

The notion of cultural landscape has often been understood as a historical and territorial reading of built forms and material heritage, particularly within the fields of cultural geography and preservation policies. As established by UNESCO, cultural landscapes are defined as “combined works of nature and humankind,” expressing the evolution of human societies in interaction with the natural environment (UNESCO, 2025, Section 47). Although this definition allows, within its associative typology, for designations grounded in religious or cultural associations even in the absence of significant material evidence, its operationalization remains anchored in processes of identification, delimitation, and management that prioritize the visible and legible configuration of the territory.

Yet this need for legibility tends to marginalize forms of existence and landscape-making that cannot be catalogued and can only be experienced. It is here that the field this article aims to discuss opens up.

In this sense, we propose to reflect on which dimensions of the cultural landscape may remain inaccessible to regimes of visibility and to explore clay as a key to thinking about that which escapes concrete record. A material situated between earth and water, between formation and dissolution, clay has the property of absorbing and condensing distinct intersections: embodied, mythical, political, and memorial, without any of them dissolving into the others. It is this constitutive porosity that makes clay a productive symbolic operator: not a metaphor that represents the landscape, but a material that allows for weaving relationships between fields that institutional discourse tends to separate.

The article thus proposes the hypothesis that clay, taken as a symbolic operator of the cultural landscape, renders legible the embodied, relational, and symbolic dimensions of the landscape that escape regimes of visibility, allowing us to understand it not as a stable form, but as a lived process.

It draws, for this purpose, on the thought of Tim Ingold (2021, 2022), for whom the landscape is not something to be contemplated from a distance, but a medium that surrounds us. In dialogue with Antônio Bispo dos Santos (2023) and drawing on reflections in recent Afro-diasporic literature, we examine how this inhabiting can be experienced as a contested practice or felt as a wound in one's own body. Next, we investigate the symbolic dimension of clay, drawing on the figure of Nanã, the orisha of the swamps in Yoruba cosmology (Zacharias & Silva, 2025), as an operator that condenses, on the mythical plane, the liminality that clay embodies on the material plane. Finally, Celeida Tostes' performance *Passagem* (1979) is analyzed as a synthesis of the argument: a bodily and symbolic gesture that, upon entering the interior of a clay pot—a space that is at once visceral and cosmological—produces a landscape not as a visible configuration, but as a lived experience, situated in the body and unrepeatable.

The conclusion draws on James Hillman's notion of *anima mundi* (2013) to suggest that, far from being populated by inert objects and landscapes delimited by their visible configurations, the world emerges as a field of sensibility in which its agents actively participate in the formation of meaning.

From a methodological standpoint, this article articulates a qualitative, essayistic approach (Adorno, 2003), analyzing literary and artistic works and religious traditions, based on the recognition that all knowledge is situated and that forms of knowledge, even when circumscribed to certain contexts, possess an analytical power capable of illuminating broader questions about the body, territory, and memory.

INHABITING THE LANDSCAPE

Tim Ingold (2022) proposes an understanding of landscape that moves away from reducing it to an image or object. For him, landscape does not present itself as something to be contemplated from a distance, but as a medium that surrounds us. Upon entering a forest, the world emerges as a field of continuously intertwining relationships: trees, soil, wind, and light manifest as processes that mutually constitute one another in the experience of the landscape.

This formulation also shifts the subject's position. If the landscape is not an object before an observer, but a medium in which one is implicated, then knowing the landscape is not reduced to describing it, but requires participating in its processes. Perception ceases to operate as the apprehension of finished forms and comes to constitute itself as our body's engagement with material and temporal flows. In this sense, the landscape is something we traverse and that, at the same time, traverses us in a dynamic field in which matter and experience are mutually implicated:

It is in the depths of the woods that the world opens itself most completely to our perception, for it forces us to abandon the illusion to which those in high places are prone, that the world we inhabit extends like a mosaic beneath our feet, with its forms and patterns already imprinted upon the physical substrate of nature (Ingold, 2022, p. 183).

In this sense, the earth presents itself not as an abstract concept, but as the ground beneath our feet; by defining where the body ends, it creates a sensory relationship with the environment, making visible the interconnection between body, matter, and landscape.

This intimate relationship with this element is present in the work of Antônio Bispo dos Santos (2023). Raised in adobe and rammed-earth houses typical of the Cerrado and the Caatinga, he learned that building with earth, while delimiting the community's occupied space, establishes relationships of belonging with the landscape. The house built on the earth brings into its interior the colors, textures, and aromas of the environment, inscribing it within a whole that is both physical and symbolic. It is in this sense that Bispo states: "You mark your home on the earth, but you also mark your home among the stars, to position yourself within a cosmological relationship" (Santos, 2023, p. 44).

This same mud house that, in Bispo, sustains relationships of belonging, in *Torto Arado*, by Itamar Vieira Junior (2020), is simultaneously a refuge and a barrier: it welcomes, but prevents belonging from taking root. In these contexts of land insecurity among quilombola communities, there is an ambiguous feeling toward the mud house, even as it establishes a relationship with the cycles of the earth: "I saw it as a wonder for a house to spring from the earth itself, from the very same mud in which, if we were to sow seeds, we would see food sprout" (Vieira Junior, 2020, p. 142), the rules prohibiting it, dictated by the farm owners, were explicit: "they could build mud houses, but no masonry, nothing that would mark the families' time on the land" (Vieira Junior, 2020, p. 41).

The apparent precariousness of these structures does not result from technical limitations, but from a political decision: the house must fall apart so that a sense of belonging does not take

root. And when the house is abandoned, the novel records the return: “the earthen wall, made of the clay that was the ground of Água Negra, became earth again” (Vieira Junior, 2020, p. 195). This erasure, however, is no exception: the absence of quilombola, Indigenous, and Afro-diasporic heritage from official records is rarely fortuitous.

As Benjamin (2022) reminds us, every cultural document is simultaneously a document of oppression, and what has not been recorded preserves, in that silence, the memory of the violence that prevented it from existing as heritage. Part of this heritage survives through narratives, bodily gestures, and ritual practices, in a form of existence that cultural protection mechanisms, as they are currently implemented, struggle to recognize.

If, in *Torto Arado*, clay highlights the denial of the guarantee of permanence in the landscape, in *Ponciá Vicêncio*, by Conceição Evaristo (2017), it persists as an inscription on the body itself. The practice of pottery, learned by the protagonist alongside her mother, asserts itself as a bond between generations, an inscription of identity, and a way of being in the world through manual work with clay.

Born on a former slave plantation, when Ponciá moves to the city and distances herself from the activity of making clay vessels and sculptures, she begins to feel this in her body, manifesting as a persistent wound: “an itch between her fingers that she scratched until it bled” (Evaristo, 2017, p. 79).

At another moment, upon dipping her hands in water, Ponciá perceives the scent of clay on them, bringing back memories of her grandfather’s presence. Clay, thus, transcends its dimension as a material and comes to constitute a subjective landscape within the character, to which she turns in the face of a hard life in the city, marked by social injustice and marital unhappiness.

This connection between earth and subjective experience is not limited to fiction. In an earth-building workshop in Lisbon that I attended, the instructor had collected samples of different soils from the region in the form of white, brown, and beige earths, some containing fragments of seashells. We discussed the importance of feeling the moisture, texture, and color when working with such a variable raw material.

When he moistened a reddish-colored sample—typical of the places where I played as a child in the interior of Minas Gerais—a colleague from Guinea-Bissau and I immediately recognized, unlike the Portuguese instructor, the characteristic smell of wet earth from our homeland. It was the water that revealed it: by forming the clay, it released what the material contained, and the scent that emerged revealed a landscape not before the eyes, but inscribed within the body, made of memories, affections, and experiences linked to our origins.

This episode makes it clear how matter, through the senses, evokes layers of memory and belonging, reaffirming the body as a living archive of the cultural landscape, in line with Ingold’s perspective when he states that “to know things, we must penetrate them and then let them grow within us, let them become a part of who we are” (Ingold, 2022, p. 11). It is at this level, where the sensory precedes intellectual elaboration, that the symbolic finds its relevance in the analysis of

cultural landscapes: it names what experience has already revealed.

BETWEEN EARTH AND WATER

Thus far, clay has been approached as a relational material and as the thread connecting experiences of landscapes that are not merely contemplated but inhabited. There is something about this material that affects us beyond its smell, its plastic resistance to touch, and its establishment of a distinct temporality in interaction. Shaping it is not limited to obtaining a form: it opens a symbolic field in which images germinate and transform. In these gestures, interaction with clay also reflects, on a personal scale, collective and ancestral contents. Rooted in the long relationship between us and this moist, dark material—associated with the feminine, the womb, and the Moon—clay carries a symbolism that invites co-authorship between subject and world: “In clay, man creates and is created” (Gouvêa, 2021, p. 73).

It is in this fertility that the symbolic emerges as something that springs from the very encounter between body and substance. The symbol is neither the property of matter nor a projection of the subject; it arises when an image points to a meaning that is still undetermined, in which visible and invisible dimensions “come together” (*symballein*), without ever exhausting themselves (Jacobi, 2021).

This understanding resonates deeply with Nagô thought, as described by Muniz Sodré (2021): in it, the human being is not separate from matter or the divine; all share the same substance, the same condition. Shaping clay, from this perspective, is not a gesture upon inert matter: it is a reunion between substances that share the same origin. In this context, the richness of Yoruba cosmology, with its intricate web of meanings, offers in the figure of Nanã a particularly potent symbolic designation for the liminal condition of clay, where material presence and cosmological power reveal themselves to be inseparable.

In Yoruba cosmology, Olorum is the supreme creative principle, and the orixás are the forces that govern the realms of the world: the waters, the metals, the forest, the dead. When Olorum decided that the Earth would be inhabited by new beings, he asked each orixá to bring matter to shape the bodies of living beings. Many took the mud in their hands, but the tears of Nanã, lady of the swamps and still waters, trickled through their fingers and made them retreat. It was Ikú, death, who took a portion of the mud and brought it to Olorum, who recognized in it the perfect raw material. As reparation to Nanã, it was established that death would return to the soil, in due time, everything that was taken from it to create life (Prandi, 2002; Zacharias & Silva, 2025).

Nanã’s realm, like clay, exists between earth and water. In this transitional space, form is not definitive, but part of a continuous cycle of creation and dissolution. Nanã governs this interval, and what she reveals is not only impermanence, but the primacy of relationships and processes over any form of fixation. What this realm reveals is that what is real lies not in stable forms, but in the relational processes that traverse them. Impermanence is the condition that makes the creation of meaning possible, because meaning always emerges in relation.

This aspect finds resonance in what Ingold (2022), drawing on Simondon, says about clay: it has no form of its own; it takes the form of the encounter. Shaping clay is bringing two chains of transformation together to a point of compatibility, at which the clay can take on the mold and the mold can take on the clay. Form emerges from this tension; it does not precede it.

When we shift this reflection to the cultural landscape, we find an analogous condition: heritage possesses a processual dimension—lived and embodied—that precedes any crystallization. However, mechanisms of recognition operate primarily on stabilized forms, apprehending that which has already acquired defined contours. As Tim Ingold proposes, the things of the world of life “are their stories, identified not by fixed attributes, but by their trajectories of movement within a field of unfolding relations” (2021, p. 327), and it is precisely this dimension that eludes the instruments of protection.

Laurajane Smith (2023) identifies in what she calls the Authorized Discourse of Heritage (DAP) the mechanism that produces it. For Smith, “heritage is best conceptualized as a process, practice, or performative activity in which meaning is continually made and remade” (2023, p. 123), with material objects serving as cultural tools that aid this fabrication, not heritage itself. AHD reverses this logic: it focuses attention on aesthetically legible and stable objects, authorizing experts as their guardians. The paradox is that the very criteria that define what deserves to be recognized as heritage are themselves the result of “embodied practices and speech acts that continually create and recreate meaning” (2023, p. 124), that is, the regime that presents itself as the guardian of the permanent is itself fluid and historically situated. What is at stake, therefore, is not only the difficulty of recognizing heritage in its non-material dimensions, but the regime—albeit itself process-based—that privileges the ruin at the expense of the process.

It is in Celeida Tostes’ performance *Passagem* (1979) that this focus on the process over the object finds its most radical expression in the field of the arts, and its most concrete response to what institutional mechanisms fail to achieve.

PASSAGEM

Celeida Tostes (1929–1995), a visual artist and ceramist from Rio de Janeiro, is a central figure in the renewal of ceramics as an artistic language in 1970s Brazil, a time when the field was shifting from the utilitarian object to the gesture and from the artifact to the process. Her practice engages with certain principles of Brazilian Neoconcretism, a movement that broke with formalism and reinserted art into the lived world. Inspired by the philosophy of Merleau-Ponty (1908–1961), Neoconcretism proposed that the artist engage with time and space as dimensions that emerge from experience, not separate from it. There is, moreover, a strongly symbolic character in Celeida’s work: she explores clay as a material of the feminine, of fertility, of motherhood, of birth, and of death, inscribing these themes as an embodied experience in the very manipulation of the clay.

It is within this framework that the performance *Passagem* (Passage; 1979) establishes a full-body ritual. Covered in liquid clay, her assistants build a large amphora of raw clay around her

body (Figure 1). Unlike modeled clay, which is restricted to the touch of the hand, liquid clay fills the contours of the entire body, becoming an intermediate surface that belongs neither entirely to the material nor entirely to the subject. The vessel, an ancestral and shared form, condenses from its very construction a network of actions, knowledge, and presences, and the authorship of the work dissolves into the collective gesture involving multiple subjects.

Figure 1: Celeida Tostes, *Passagem*, 1979, photograph, courtesy of Galeria Superfície.

The fetal position inside the vessel, as it closes around the artist, evokes the liminality that Nanã condenses on the cosmological plane. The dissolution of the boundary between subject and matter, between form and formlessness, between emergence and reintegration is what Bachelard (2003, p. 4) recognized as the fundamental structure of the material imagination linked to the earth: “the house, the womb, the cave bear the same great mark of the return to the mother.” The body that curls in on itself and allows itself to be enveloped by matter inhabits precisely this space between welcoming and imprisonment.

From this dark and damp environment, Celeida breaks out of the vessel to escape (Figure 2) and, in doing so, undoes the form of the object that contained her. Something analogous to this

gesture can be recognized in Merleau-Ponty's text when he observes that "the absolute position of a single object is the death of consciousness, since it immobilizes all experience" (2022, p. 109). The sealed vessel would be exactly that: a crystallized form, an object isolated from everything that generated it. By breaking it, Celeida rejects this immobilization and returns to the world the process that had unfolded within the vessel.

After this experience, she recorded the intensity of the experience in words:

I stripped myself
I covered my body in clay and went.
I entered the belly of darkness, the womb of the earth.
Time lost its sense of time.
I reached the formless.
I may have been mineral, animal, plant.
I don't know what I was.
I don't know where I was. Space.
History no longer existed.
Sounds resonated.
They came from me.
Pain.
I don't know where I walked.
The darkness, the sounds, the pain, all mingled together.
Transmutation.
Space shrank.
I left. I returned. (Tostes, 2014, p. 52, translation by the author)

Passagem brings together the two dimensions that clay embodies throughout this article. The first is phenomenological: the body that is implicated in the landscape, which does not exist as an isolated object, but in the embodied experience of the world's constitution. The second is symbolic: it is constituted in the encounter between gesture and the world. The smell of clay on Ponciá's hands, already mentioned, evokes the grandfather without representing him. Celeida's body inside the vase traverses the origin without illustrating it. The symbolic is lived, embodied, and it is precisely from there that its strength comes.

That is where the unifying character of clay lies: because it is a concrete, resistant, tactile material, it can be a vehicle for symbolic content without abstracting itself from the body. Clay does not illustrate the symbol: it is the place where it is embodied. It allows us to speak of the subtle without abandoning the present, of the ancestral without abandoning the body, because it keeps them together, in the same substance. It is Nanã's clay inhabited by the living body.

CONCLUSION

This article proposed rethinking the cultural landscape as a field of lived relationships, beyond its fixation on territorial forms. The analysis reveals that clay, like the landscape itself, is not passive. It sustains the sense of belonging in Antônio Bispo dos Santos and negates it in *Torto Arado*; it

Figure 2: Celeida Tostes, *Passagem*, 1979, photograph, courtesy of Galeria Superficie.

embraces the body in Celeida Tostes' performance and marks it by its absence, as in Ponciá's hands.

It is also concrete, resistant, tactile, and it is precisely for this reason that it can carry symbolic content without abstracting itself from its material dimension. This quality, which consists of holding together the tangible and the subtle, the corporeal and the ancestral, is what constitutes it as an operator for rethinking the cultural landscape as a necessarily fluid and open-ended concept.

In this sense, clay converges with the notion of *anima mundi* developed by James Hillman (2013). For Hillman, the soul resides not only within the subject, but in the very things of the world, in objects, in images, in matter. The world, thus, presents a face, depth, and appeal, and demands a form of listening. This conception challenges the modern separation between soul and world and calls us to participate in things not as distant observers, but as bodies implicated in a process that precedes and exceeds us.

This perspective deepens the understanding of landscape as a field of unfolding relations, as proposed by Tim Ingold (2022), and aligns with Muniz Sodré in suggesting that the world is not only dynamic but endowed with its own interiority, capable of addressing and returning the gaze.

If the problem with landscape lies in its tendency to be limited by its visible and territorial configuration, what this article proposes is an expansion of this concept toward a sensory and symbolic dimension that is constitutive of it. The landscape that Celeida reveals in *Passagem* is,

in this sense, vast and productive: it opens up within matter and the body, summoning origins, returns, and affiliations that challenge the mechanisms of identification of traditional heritages.

By breaking the vase to escape, Celeida restores to the world that which had been momentarily silenced from it. This gesture can be understood, with James Hillman, as a return that not only restores to the world what was taken from it, but transforms the way of seeing: a second gaze, which recognizes in things not only form, but presence.

It is in this second gaze that an expansion of the concept of cultural landscape is proposed: a landscape grounded not only in vision, but also in listening. In this sense, the landscape becomes an interlocutor, and what is established between it and the subject is not merely a presence in the territory, but the recognition of a life that unfolds in relation.

This implies shifting the criteria of preservation from an exclusive emphasis on form to an attention to the practices, gestures, and relationships that sustain the continuity of landscapes. As Laurajane Smith points out, heritage production already occurs on multiple scales—in oral histories, family legacies, and informal community practices—even though the institutional sphere remains, to a large extent, tied to criteria that prioritize visible and durable forms.

It is in this gap—between what is already recognized and what still eludes recognition—that the need for instruments capable of embracing processes, ways of doing, and ways of inhabiting as central dimensions of cultural heritage becomes evident. In this context, clay presents itself not only as a material but as a symbolic operator: a means of rendering otherwise invisible relationships sensible and legible.

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